

THE USE OF GRAPHIC SCHEMES DURING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE SUBJECT AS A FOREIGN IN A MODERN UZBEK SCHOOL

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Annotation. This article discusses the use of graphic organizers in the Russian language classes - the creation of positive motivation for schoolchildren; involvement in various activities; providing a choice of memorizing material; application of thinking visualization technology (i.e. structuring information).

Keywords: graphic organizers, application of technology, motivation of schoolchildren, visual representation, research activity, development of analytical, critical and creative abilities.

Introduction:

Method (Greek "metodos" - a way of cognition or research, theory, teaching) - a set of techniques, techniques for creating and substantiating philosophical knowledge, practical and theoretical acquisition, mastery, study of reality.

Technology is a well-thought-out system for translating a goal into specific item or action. "Teaching technology" is a component procedural part of the didactic system (M. Choshanov).

Active techniques and teaching methods contribute to the implementation of the objectives of the lesson and activate mental activity, the development of critical thinking, the formation of functional literacy of students. Most importantly, the teacher must understand that the use of active methods and forms of work determines the approach to the content and development of the modern developing educational environment, increasing the motivation of students in the learning process, because students must not only "get" knowledge, but master the methods of cognition, that is, learn to study.

Graphic tables are the most effective integral part of active methods and pedagogical technology in the lessons of the Russian language and literature. I consider the graphic organizer, which I will discuss in more detail today, important for the study of a particular subject. Graphic organizers are anything that somehow helps to organize information on a piece of paper (or computer screen) in order to improve its memorization, assimilation, analysis or application.

In the process of visualizing information, the student thinks, comprehends, passes information through himself, presenting it in a visual-conceptual way. Students master the methods of searching, confirming, systematizing and arguing information, finding interdisciplinary connections.

Graphical representation of information contributes to the development of the ability to work with text, because. allows you to learn to formulate the main idea, highlight key words, divide the text into structural parts, collapse information in the form of secondary sources (plan, algorithm, table, diagram), expand it ("read" formulas, equations), recode from visual to verbal and vice versa .

The use of graphic tables improves the potential of students' knowledge:

- improves reading comprehension;
- improves the memorization of information - in the case when it is presented both visually and in text form;
- academic performance is growing, including for students with learning difficulties, critical thinking skills, typology of graphic organizers are improving.

In the process of compiling a "fish skeleton", students master the following skills:

- learn to work in a group or pairs;
- develop critical thinking;
- learn to formulate the main idea;
- select key words;
- divide the text into parts.

Graphic table, often used in literature lessons

I consider the graphic organizer, which I will discuss in more detail today, important for the study of certain subjects. Consider one of the practical techniques, the Fishbone graphic organizer, which we can use in the lessons of the Russian language and literature.

The Fishbone method, literally translated from English as "Fish Skeleton", the simplified name of the method of the Japanese scientist Kaoru Ishikawa, is also designed to develop creative thinking and analytical skills in working with information.

This graphical organizer for presenting information allows you to figuratively demonstrate the course of the analysis of a phenomenon by highlighting the problem, finding out its causes and supporting facts, and formulating a conclusion on the issue.

The advantage of this methodological technique is to establish causal relationships between the object of study and the factors influencing it.

Visually, the Fishbone diagram is an image that indicates the main four blocks, illustrated in the form of a head, tail, upper and lower bones. All parts are connected by the main link - the ridge of the fish.

So, the head is the question, the main topic to be studied. The top bones are the main concepts of the topic, or the reasons that led to the emergence of the main topic. Lower bones are facts that confirm the presence of upper bones (causes). The final link is the tail, which should answer the main question or serve as a generalization to the indicated causal data.

Conclusion:

Thus, we can conclude that the correct use of the organizer by the teacher "Fishbone" in the classroom contribute to the transfervisual images and complex information

in an easy-to-understand way; development of analytical, critical and creative abilities, the ability to plan. There is a huge variety of graphic organizers: tables, trees, clusters, mental maps, etc., but they all play an important role in the process of formative assessment in the classroom. With their help, you can check how students can compare information, concepts on several aspects; establish causal relationships.

Teachers and students can use the graphic "Fishbone" for the development of language skills, since the student, when using graphic schemes, gets the opportunity to conduct his own research, take his first steps into an interesting world of discovery. The student compiles an answer algorithm that includes key information, on the basis of which he subsequently builds his answer. The teacher gives the opportunity to lead the student's research activities, support the student in achieving learning goals and meeting educational needs.

As a result, we can prioritize information, determine which parts of the material are the most important and which are secondary, be able to place each element in a certain place.

Each teacher chooses methods that are more suitable for him, today I gave an example of the most active Fishbone method, which I use in Russian language and literature lessons and achieve excellent results.

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